

A Qualitative Study Of Attributes Of A Good Teacher As Perceived By Pupils And Principals

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 28, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 12, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teacher Attributes, Higher Education, Student's Perception, Principal's Perception</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4681321</p>	<p><i>The present study was conducted on exploring the attributes of a good teacher as perceived by pupils and principals. The purpose of the study was to explore the attributes of a good teacher perceived by pupils and principals and explore the difference among these perceptions. The study was carried out into two group pupils and principals. A qualitative approach was used as research method for this study. Sample consisted of 30 participants (Students) of 9th grade in which 15 were girls and 15 were boys while 6 were (Principals) of 6 government schools in which 3 were males and 3 were females. Age range of (Students) participants was (15-17 years). Purposive sampling was used for this study. Semi-structured interviews were conducted, and data was analyzed by manual coding method. Eight common themes were perceived. First theme was competency in subject, second theme was kind behavior with students, and third theme was presentable, and fourth theme was role model, fifth theme was democratic, sixth theme groomed personality, 7th theme trustworthy and eight theme was friendly. Results and implications are discussed.</i></p>

Introduction

Education includes teaching, learning, specific skills; the influence of learning, a positive judgment and a well-developed wisdom Education has the transmission of culture from generation to generation as one of its fundamental aspects. Training implies "the growth of an individual's self-potential and latent talents." (Anonymous, 2008).

Education in Pakistan

Education in Pakistan is split into five grades: primary (1st to 5th grades), secondary (6th to 8th grades), medium (nine-and-tenth grade) and intermediate (11th and 12th grades) and university graduation. The provincial government is responsible for all academic institutions. Pakistan's education system typically consists of six stages. Pre-school (3-5 years), main (1-5 grade) Middle (6-8 grade) and higher school (9-10 grade) contribute to SSC and intermediate (11-12 grade). "Education is a matter of Pakistan's existence and death. The environment is changing so quickly that not only do we fall behind many but we can wake up completely without the requisite change in education". (Quaid e azam 1947).

Principal

A principal, headmaster and headmistress is the oldest teacher in a school. A principal is typically the middle, mid-sized or large school chief executive. The United States has nearly 129,000 administrators in 1999. One or more vice presidents, assistant directors or deputy directors support the boss. In relation to school governance, their role is subordinate to the principal.

Pupil

The pupil concept describes one under academic discipline as a valuable disparity between teachers and graduates. When they attain a certain level in their state, most pupils are required to give up their schooling.

Teacher

An instructor is a recognized mentor or assistance in learning processes. Education is embodied in all that exists, at the most profound transformation of type and organizational aggregator, which ensures that the actual participating in the learning cycle creates some kind of sense and has substantive interactions in ecosystems. A teacher is always instructed by his pupil. A tutor may be described as an instructor, who teaches directly. (Anonymous, 2007).

Attributes of good teacher

Efficient teaching is a continuous learning cycle and improvements are brought on every academic year by professional instructors. Students, curricula, building problems peers, administrators, budgets, safety, welfare, families, societies and various other factors on teacher daily life will alter.

Problem Statement

A good teacher is very important for children's teaching, personality and socialization. Specific inquiries revealed the variability of a strong teacher's characteristics and illustrated the different expectations of pupils and principals. The researcher hopes to achieve the following research goals:

- 1) To find the difference of perception of good teacher by Pupils and principals.
- 2) To examine the impact of Different perceptions on achievement.

Therefore this present study was attempt to investigate the perceptions, difference among perception and will be helpful to understand the impact of their difference on achievement. It will also be helpful for further researches at different levels of teaching for college lecturers, university professors.

It is hoped that this research will provide an answer to following research question: What are the qualities of a good teacher perceived by pupils and principals?

Review of literature

Sheikh & Iqbal (2003) We are now living in a world which is full of complex and multifaceted challenges. We still face the threat of war. A host of other ills with devastating effects even come before us. Teachers are again told to consider the chance. Learners will be more than ever expected to meet a range of social demands and help people to clear the plagues of the 21st century: war, analphabetism, poverty and social injustice.

Qualities of a Good Teacher

Fredriksson (2009) Dialogue at the state , city, school and ongoing rates will decide the consistency which a specific education system pursue in good teachers and list all of the following in terms of the commonly held opinion of good teachers, as well as the appropriate knowledge of subject matter to teach confidently. Teachers are capable of developing and sustaining an effective learning and contact environment. They are involved in particular students. Such characteristics are not exercised as separate practices in each specific instructor.

Studies Based on Teachers opinions regarding Effective Teaching

Cattell (1931) early teacher productivity studies appeared not to discuss the actions of teachers in the classroom, but the attributes of teachers as age, sex and personality. "The five attributes most commonly mentioned by a successful instructor were "personality and will," "thinking," "sympathy and technique," "friendly heart," and "humor" (the five attributes were also rated top five only by high school leaders and teachers).

Studies Based on Pupils opinions regarding Effective Teaching

Taylor (1962) published findings of a survey of 'healthy teachers' traits, which included a selection of 397 high school pupils whose instruction, training and personal characteristics were required to be rated. The overall picture that emerged, that the good teacher is firm and in class, is fair and punishable, is fair and helps you do what you have to do, and is friendly to kids at and off school.

Effective Teaching and Student Academic Achievement

Nuthall (2004) Training is the result and collection of a broad range of tools. There is no mystery regarding the value of a successful teacher. Schools and their families should get the finest instructors they will trust their students excel. Teacher success is more often measured in terms of academic achievement, and is simpler and less expensive than any other primary measures of successful schooling. Given this, some scholars suggest that student learning will not be quite as relevant to teachers as student behavior, incentive control of resources and tasks in time.

Other Factors of Student Achievement

Greenwald, Hedges & Liane, (1996) the question of how the efficacy of teachers varies significantly in fostering academic success in educational studies. If disparities in teacher effectiveness are common, it is necessary for basic research and for change in education to recognize more successful teachers and the reasons that make them more efficient. There is no justification for a prominent reviewers of output functions to conclude that calculated professorial characteristics such as preparation, expertise or compensation are related to student success (Hanushek, 1986). Other scholars suggest that some of the features of services, including familiarity with teachers and professional preparation, have beneficial consequences. Nevertheless, several of these literature reviews conclude that, because they may be associated with the effects of unattended people, communities, colleges, and neighborhoods, it is challenging to understand the association between school or instructor attributes and successes after student background checks.

Methodology

The purpose of this segment is to explain the technique used to discover the impression of a person regarding a successful teacher's qualities.

Aim of Research

The purpose of the study is to investigate the following research question.

- 1) What are the qualities of a good teacher perceived by pupils and principals?

Qualitative Approach

A qualitative approach was chosen as the research method for this study. A qualitative approach was considered more relevant to undertake this research as it allowed greater capacity to gain more depth and meaning based on an individual (Pupils, Principal)'s perception about qualities of a good teacher along with their differences.

Participant Recruitment

For this study 36 participants were chosen in which 30 were pupils and 6 were principals. The process of recruitment was "face to face" used after taking permission by the head of the institute. It was allowed to go to the 9th grade class. The 6 government schools that were selected for research purpose or data collection.

5 pupils from each school with one of its principals were selected as participants for. This sampling process was purposive sampling method. The inclusion criteria are focused on participants (pupils, principals) of 6 government schools of Multan city. The key pupils of 30 (15 male, 15 female) 6 principals (3 male, 3 female) grade 9th aged (15-17) were chosen. While 10 students were initially recruited for the interview (8 pupil, 2 principal)

Data Collection

For data collection semi-structured interviews were used/ conducted, individually. To maintain confidentiality and ethical consideration individual interview was conducted in a setting instead of in front of all. Interviews were collected in the absence of class teacher. For interview, interview protocol or semi structured interview questions were established that were four in numbers and changeable in sequence to can be asked the participant. All participants were guided about central question and objectives. Open ended questions were used for this study (Pupil) for data collection 2-3 visits were conducted of each institute due to the availability of the participants. All interviews were recorded through audio recordings and side by side field notes were also maintained with key points. An example of an open ended question in the interview schedule is "what should a good teacher possess in your view?"

Data Analysis

The data were then marked, checked and transcribed. The transcribed interviews can help the researcher to learn more about the topic by reading the transcribed interviews repeatedly. For data analysis manual coding method was used. In first stage of coding analysis, labels or codes were assigned to words or phrases that represented important, recurring and relevant to the topic in each response. These labels or codes/categories were 30 in numbers that were found after transcribed data. Coding qualitative analysis find common themes and concepts is part of thematic analysis which is part of qualitative analysis. In the 2nd stage data was analysed common patterns were detected or any correlation or variation in the data was highlighted. This highlighted data was used for generating themes. That were 8 in numbers.

Findings

The study of the data shows that a good teacher should have all these attributes.

Competency of subject

Principals mainly focused on this attribute "A good teacher must be the master of his subject," one said likewise "a good teacher should instruct very well."

Kind behavior with students

The majority of participants reacted the same way "a good teacher should be respectful, kind-hearted, display 'positive disposition'.

Presentable

Many students claimed "A successful instructor would be portrayed in all fields including, e.g., communication abilities, dress, manner of expression, body language, accent, content and performance abilities."

Role Model

In general, a teacher is regarded by his students as a role model. Students obey or copy the behavior and manners of the teachers.

Democratic

Many students shared that 'A good instructor should be equal to all student and accessible to listening to the pupils'.

Groomed Personality

The teacher will be most particularly enthusiastic about their career. A lead participant defined "A successful instructor should be well-preserved, self-disciplinary, characteristic of a groomed personality (good health, personal grooming, smart, loving, trained, soft speaking)."

Trust worthy

A strong or healthy relationship between students and teachers is necessary for better learning or progressive learning. "A successful instructor would have a safe, trustworthy partnership with the students. Students should trust and talk to their teacher about their feelings

Friendly

Nearly all participants identified the following as "A successful instructor needs to be polite to his / her students, but within a small range".

Discussion

The result of this research suggest that characteristics of a good teacher have positive consequences such as friendly, democratic, polite, practice etc. and there is no major difference among expectations of principals and pupils. While teacher qualities have a great impact on students learning. Interviewer tried his best to be unbiased during the collection and analysis of the data.

This thesis sought to investigate the understanding by students and supervisors of the quality of a successful instructor. This study understands how these two groups perceive these attributes differently and what their impacts are on the education system. The key focus in all thirty six interviews is supposed to be "subject integrity." Both qualified members within his / her area of expertise.

As the findings of this research have demonstrated, the students find a successful professor to be a tutor, compassionate, inspired, responsible, honest, wise, comfortable, normal, timely and trustworthy. Many students have an outstanding temperament, enthusiastically respectful and committed while a strong teacher would be safe.

Another important attribute for students of research findings is the kind behavior of "kindness," which is common to students in class. There is no significant difference of opinion or interpretation among a group of pupils about a good teacher, boys and girls speak of the adverse effect of the teacher's physical punishment. While the teachers mentioned are girls that are gentle, polite and trustworthy. As "Role Model," all pupil group participants want to be their teacher.

In the second group of directors who are far older than pupils not only in physical age but also in their work experience. The six participants mentioned the same characteristic of a highly trained instructor. It was assumed that without this dimension, no teacher could succeed with his students. They see a good professor, a well-preserved, trustworthy, optimistic and inclusive identity keeper as well.

Participants mentioned the willingness of a successful instructor to consider and recognize the difference between students and to handle them as necessary. Everybody reflected their age on this egalitarian trait in which a instructor was identical to everybody and still available to all. Particularly essential for all classes is the well-presented quality. Some participants would like to see the instructor truthful, cheerful, polite and disciplined.

Interview Protocol

- 1) According to your Point of view "What should be the qualities of a good teacher with respect to education"?
- 2) Which type of relationship good teachers have with their students?
- 3) What should be the personality of a good teacher?

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